

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING THE METHODOLOGY OF WRITING FORMAL LETTERS

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Abstract In this article, we explain what an official letter is and how to write one, plus we provide a template and example of an official letter for you to reference.

Key words: Official letter, important information, document, formal letter, informal letter, Set up your font and margins.

Аннотация В этой статье мы объясняем, что такое официальное письмо и как его написать, а также предоставляем шаблон и пример официального письма, на который вы можете ссылаться.

Ключевые слова: Официальное письмо, важная информация, документ, официальное письмо, неофициальное письмо, настройте свой шрифт и поля.

One way to express an opinion or provide important information to others can be through an official letter. This is a professional way to explain yourself while using simple, concise sentences to avoid taking up the reader's time. Official letters follow a specific structure or format that must be maintained throughout the entire document.

An official letter, also known as a "formal letter," is a document professionally written for another company or business professional. They can be used when applying for jobs, issuing a complaint, expressing interest in a job position or thanking someone. Official letters are often written using simple and direct sentences with a formal greeting and signature included. Writing an official letter typically requires following a very structured and specific format.

Creating a concise and clear official letter can help explain your intent and purpose in a way your audience may easily understand. Follow the steps below to learn how to write an official letter.

Set up your font and margins

Before you begin, you want to ensure your letter is not only simple to understand, but simple to read as well. To keep your letter clean and professional, you should set your margins to be one inch per each side of the document. Using simple fonts like Verdana, Arial, Calibri or Times New Roman with a 12-point size will give your official letter a clean look as well.

Create your heading

Once your fonts are set, you can begin addressing your letter. First, write your name in the top left-hand corner of the page. Include your name, address and the current date. You can also include your phone number and email if you are requesting further contact.

You can now input the recipient's address information directly beneath yours. Write their name, title of their organization if they are representing one, followed by the address. Review the name and address of your recipient more than once to ensure you've written the correct address and spelled their name right.

Write your salutation

You can now professionally greet your reader. A common salutation used in official letters is, "Dear Ms. or Mr. Last name". If you know both their first name or last name, you can include that in the salutation. For example, you can write, "Dear Alex Smith". If you know their gender, you can write, "Dear Mr. Alex Smith" or "Dear Ms. Alex Smith". If you're unaware of the name of the recipient, consider alternatives to using "Dear Sir or Madam."

The body paragraphs are where you can capture your main points and professionally explain your concerns, opinions or other information to your recipient. You can briefly introduce yourself and begin by explaining your reason for writing this letter. You can use verbiage such as, "I am writing to you today because..."

Once you've explained what the recipient will read, you can expand further throughout the next paragraph. Include details that support your first statement. For example, if you were writing a recommendation letter, you could expand on the skills of the person your recommending by saying, "Avery's time-management and organizational skills have improved the efficiency of my business by 12% since the beginning of the quarter."

You can continue giving examples until you believe your point has been clearly understood by the reader. Keep your sentences short, simple and easy for the reader to understand.

To finalize your letter, you can write your conclusion paragraph. This paragraph can be short and will finalize the document by repeating your main point, explaining any possible next steps or thanking the recipient for taking the time to read your letter.

After closing the letter, you can provide your closing signature at the end of the document.

Examples of common letter signatures are:

- Sincerely
- Sincerely yours
- With appreciation
- Thank you
- Regards
- Yours truly
- Respectfully yours

Select your closing signature and write your name at the bottom of the letter.

Enclosures are additional materials added to your letter to support your document, similar to when you attach a file to an email. If you're attaching a document to complement your letter, you should mention it near the end of your letter. To inform the reader that an additional document is attached, you can include the word "enclosure" at the end of the letter after your name. You can also shorten the word by writing, "encl." After you've finished writing, you can read through the letter to catch any grammatical or spelling errors. You can also review it to ensure it makes sense and is clear enough for the recipient to understand. Once proofread, you can send the letter to the recipient. Pick a plain white, square or rectangular envelope. Fold the letter properly so it fits in the envelope. Write your name and address in the top left-hand corner of the envelope followed by the recipient's name and address in the middle. Put a stamp on the right-hand corner and send your letter to the desired recipient.

Since both official and unofficial letters are written documents used to send messages to others, it may be easy to confuse the two.

Official letters are often:

- Typed and never handwritten

- Following strict, standard grammar and English rules
- Containing short and concise sentences
- Using a specific, professional structure

Unofficial letters don't follow a structure as strict as official letters. Instead, official letters contain:

- Less professional and more casual language
- Words that are handwritten or typed
- No specific type of formatting or structure they have to follow

People may write official letters for various reasons that involve professionally expressing their interests, concerns or disagreements. Common official letter types can include:

Resignation letters

When an employee leaves their current position, they may send a brief resignation letter to their employer or hiring manager to explain their reason for leaving and to develop a plan for their transition process.

Cover letters

Writing a cover letter is one of the most common uses for official letters. Applicants can write cover letters when applying for a new job position, grant programs or educational programs.

Complaint letters

Many individuals or companies may use an official letter structure to express a complaint with a product or service. An employee may be asked to write a complaint letter on behalf of a company who is dissatisfied with a product used by its employees.

Professional thank you notes

After a job interview, an applicant may write a professional thank you note to express their gratitude to the employer for meeting with them and considering them for the position.

Knowing how to write a business letter will serve you well throughout your career. Keep practicing and studying it, and you'll be able to communicate in a classic style.

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